

1 **Ribosomal activation in TNBC resistance *in vitro*.**

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7 We describe ribosomal activation in TNBC resistance *in vitro*. 5S ribosomal genes were most significantly
8 affected. This included RNA5S1, RNA5S17 and RNA5S8. Ribosomal protein *RPS6* was induced. *Rpl21*
9 and *Rps17* were also both highly activated in expression supporting mobilization of ribosomal energy
10 resources during a clinical encounter associated with administration of chemotherapy which resulted in a
11 resistance response.

12 Citations

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